

COMPARISON ANALYSIS ON DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR ENHANCING NETWORK SECURITY

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Abstract:

This paper explores various security issues in networks and the various types of attacks processed by malicious users and attackers. This study also proposed a safety for network risk analysis using a network of a system. Big Data, Cloud Computing and other advanced technologies are completely utilized by the survey system to accurately detect any network security threads and make an effort to alert user and pertinent departments of any ongoing security threads. This paper analyzed supervised learning methods and unsupervised learning methods in machine learning used for Intrusion Detection. The comparison results showed that the supervised learning methods are more effective in IDS detection when compared with unsupervised learning methods.

Keywords: Network Security, Machine Learning, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Intrusion Detection System (IDS)

1. INTRODUCTION

In rapid development of information technology, Security of data is primarily considered worldwide. The modern environments adopt new advanced technologies to secure their data from various attackers. Network security represents the steps processed for ensuring protection in computer network where the data transaction is primarily achieved. This security is majorly required for all types of networks to keep their network safe and ensure the confidentiality of sensitive data in computer. Cyber attacks are the main threads for network security which considers the vulnerabilities in network to compromise security policies. Due to the growth of massive communication networks, the large amount of data transaction is processed all over the

world. The increased number of malicious users intentionally attacks and damage the sources which are connected with network(Guo, 2024). The intruders with hidden agendas target government agencies and militaries for getting security information for financial benefits. Data Encryption methods are used to avoid the security issues while data transmission. The Cryptography is one of the powerful techniques which allows people to make secure data transaction. The modern cryptography techniques are used to improve the security standards to avoid data leakage and data breaches. These techniques are widely adopted and used to increase the privacy of user data and data integrity maintenance.

2. NETWORK SECURITY

Network security includes authorization of user generally with username and password verification. There are some advanced methods incorporated in this by adapting two-way verification by sending one-time password to user's registered mobile number or email. This ensured the strong verification of user to allow them for resource utilization. The network security for organization includes policies which indicates the permissions and restrictions of network resource utilization by people inside and outside of that organization. This helps the network administrator to monitor the unauthorized access of user of resources. The insiders and outsiders' attacks for data access can also be monitored and protected using security methods(Chen, 2024). The attackers are focusing the network vulnerabilities adapted by the organization. The weaknesses are utilized by intruders and attackers to compromise the security policies and gain access of data utilization. The strong policies and multi-level verification for user authentication is more important to avoid data loss. The sensitive information access must be verified in various level to avoid data leakage. The security policies must cover the entire network process to avoid serious issues related to data losses and breaches(Mao, 2023).

The secure network must consider the following components for enhancing protection in various levels of data transaction

User Authentication: The user verification is the major process for ensuring respective user by verifying their registered user name and password(Al-Haija, 2024).

Access Permission: The data access limit of the user must be ensured by their roles and responsibilities addressed by administrator.

Data Confidentiality: The data must be edited and updated by proper user who has rights for changing it. This data updating verification and removal verification must be done by administrator for avoiding loss.

Data integrity:The changes made by user about data must be verified to ensure the reliability of data that is stored and processed.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The different machine learning approaches used for network security is reviewed in this work. The types of machine learning techniques are focused in this study.

3.1 Supervised Learning Techniques for Network Security

The supervised learning algorithms are efficient in intrusion detection and malware identification which can ensure the security in network. The Support Vector Machine Method, Decision trees with Boosting and Bagging, K-Nearest neighbour methods are popularly used for finding malwares and intrusion finding in network.

JayShree Jha and Leena Ragma (Jayshree Jha., 2023) proposed the SVM based intrusion detection system. They used information gain and K-Means algorithm which are incorporated with SVM method for its enhanced prediction. For this work they used NSL-KDD dataset which is used for intrusion detection. Jie Hu et.al. (Jie Gu., 2021) proposed a new enhanced SVM method with Naïve Bayes feature embedding for intrusion detection. The feature transformation technique is applied using Naïve Bayes method and the detection is based on SVM model. This proposed model achieved improved accuracy with various datasets like 93.75% accuracy in UNSW-NB15 dataset, 98.92% accuracy in CICID2017 dataset, 99.35% in NSL-KDD dataset. Lihua Su et.al. (Lihua Su., 2021) proposed experimental based intrusion detection using Support Vector Machine. For this work they used KDDCUP99 dataset. This dataset contains four different types of attacks namely Denial of Service attack (DOS), Remote access of Unauthorized (R2L) attack, Illegal access to the local super user (U2R) attack and Probing attack. This proposed model achieved 95% accuracy in intrusion detection. Abdullah Al-Saleh (Abdullah Al-Saleh., 2023) proposed a smart intrusion detection with the Support Vector Machine decision tree using a balanced communication-avoiding method. The proposed Noval IDS model incorporated with Gini Index which helped to find the impurity in selected features. This would be considered for

refinement process to reduce the impurity in feature selection. For this work UNSW-NB 15 dataset is used and SVM method was applied for detecting IDS. This model achieved 98.5% accuracy which was showed in experimental results. Chao Wang et.al. (Chao Wang., 2023)proposed one class Support Vector Machine with Gaussian Mixture Model for IDS. This model used auto encoder for representing features. The SVM with Gaussian model was trained to derived features. The experimental results showed that the use of Autoencoder and Novel SVM method increased detection rate than theother existing methods. Two different datasets are used in this work namely BoT-IoT dataset and IDS2018 dataset. The performance of Noval SVM methods was analyzed with two different datasets and the results showed that the proposed method provided enhanced accuracy in IDS.

3.2 Unsupervised Learning Techniques for Network Security

Miel Verkerken et.al. (Miel Verkerken., 2020)proposed an unsupervised learning techniques for network intrusion detection on Modern data. This proposed work focused for anomaly-based detection using flow-based features. For this work CIC-IDS-2017 dataset is used and the experimental result showed that the Receiver Operating Characteristics of proposed model reached 0.978. Jun Fang and Cunxiang Xie(Jun Fang., 2025) proposed unsupervised learning method and open-set recognition for unknown traffic detection. In this work, the OpenMax algorithm was executed on closed set where the intrusion traffic calculation was done. Then the activation vector was processed to find the unknown category in traffic. This work utilized CICIDS2017 dataset and the results showed that the proposed model achieved 88.5% accuracy in intrusion detection. Cina et.al. (Cinà, 2022)presented a survey analysis for machine learning techniques for security. The Convolutional Neural Network and Recurrent Neural Networks are experiment for network security analysis. The experimented models are provided good accuracy in detection in different datasets.

4. COMPARISON ANALYSIS FOR SUPERVISED LEARNING AND UNSUPERVISED LEARNING

There are so many different approached applied for detecting intrusion at various level to enhance the network security. Based on the performance of supervised and unsupervised learning methods in machine learning the performance comparison is considered. The supervised learning methods are highly effective in known attacks and the clear interpretability can be given

by the models why that particular event is flagged as intrusion. The specific attacks classifications are done by supervised learning methods. For detecting unknown attacks, the unsupervised learning methods are used. These techniques do not require any labelled data to train the model for detection and classification. These models are effective while handling large volume of data in process. The adaptability is comparatively high than supervised techniques. The computational cost for the supervised and unsupervised learning techniques high while using large volume of data.

5. CONCLUSION

The supervised learning methods and unsupervised learning methods are effective in known and unknown attacks respectively. The supervised methods performance are highly dependable on the data quality which is used for training and testing. Both techniques are powerful in detection of attacks in different types. In further, the Hybrid approach will be considered for detecting intrusion to ensure the robustness and efficiency. This hybrid model can be trained with less amount of labelled data for known IDS detection and deploy separate models for detecting unknown threads.

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